

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CHEBANI****FIRST NAME: TAMPIWA****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2010 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing Academic Essays (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–10)
2. Use of Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 16–22)
3. English Variants (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25–32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34–38)
5. Style Guides (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41–50)

ACADEMIC WRITING FOR DOCTORAL STUDENTS

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D focuses on the technicalities of academic writing. The course pack by Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021 thoroughly explains the expectations of academic writing.

The first chapter outlines the steps to follow when writing academic essays (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6–14). These include researching the topic, organizing ideas, and then writing. Proper punctuation is discussed as part of this writing process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15–23). Over and above proper punctuation, an academic essay must be original while drawing from existing research. Failure of originality constitutes plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33–39). The subtle differences between American and British are highlighted in Chapter 3. Particular attention is given to the use of quotation marks and commas (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31–32).

In Chapter 5, the authors discuss styles and style guides. They also present arguments to justify the need for style guides. Additionally, chapter 6 expands on the previous chapter by detailing the Chicago style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 43–57).

Since academic writing often employs Latin abbreviations, Chapter 7 elaborates on the use and meaning of Latin abbreviations and expressions. Chapter 8 demonstrates the tutor's process of correcting response papers using Microsoft Word. Accompanying this chapter is a YouTube video of Dr. Gulma explaining the same. Lastly, in the video "Understanding Templates and Styles for ACA-401," Prof. Cleenewerck explained how to use EUCLID templates.

2) WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Academic essays are formal pieces of writing that intend to advance knowledge in a specific area of the research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Unlike fictional works, such writing draws on current and previous research findings to resolve hypotheses. The study material emphasizes the fact that academic essays must be well-planned, well-thought-out, and started early. Before starting, it is helpful to have an initial plan for the essay that includes a specific question or topic to be addressed. The next step is to research the topic using relevant and credible sources that will provide evidence for any arguments presented. While reading and researching, one must be mindful of the issue or question being addressed.

Furthermore, one has to remain as objective as possible, that is, to be balanced and consider differing and even controversial viewpoints. Once the topic has been thoroughly researched, the resulting ideas and thoughts are organized in writing. This initial draft is written in sketch form and becomes the essay plan. Writing the essay requires strict adherence to the following structure: Introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10). The essay must have a logical flow, with paragraphs providing arguments and evidence focusing on specific aspects of the topic. Finally, the essay must be referenced appropriately, edited, and submitted (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11–12).

As I interacted with the study material, I understood there is a well-defined structured way to write academic essays. Interestingly, this well-defined structure does not make it a rigid and monotonous undertaking; there is room for creative and critical thinking in the process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). Being from a primarily medical/clinical background, I have never had the opportunity to be mentored step-by-step on writing academic essays. Therefore, this course on academic writing will offer value in my doctorate degree journey.

3) USE OF PUNCTUATION MARKS

When writing academic essays, it is advised to use little punctuation while maintaining the meaning of the text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 16). The study material discusses the use of various punctuation marks. Even though I knew and used most punctuation marks, I learned to use the colon and semicolon (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 18). The colon introduces and joins a dependent clause with a preceding independent clause. On the other hand, the semicolon can separate independent clauses and lists in

which items already have commas. Before studying this chapter, I had not used these two punctuation marks in my writing: I needed to learn precisely how to use them. Another punctuation mark is the apostrophe. The apostrophe is used to show possession or for contraction (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 16–17).

Other punctuation marks were discussed, such as brackets, commas, full stops, question marks, quotation marks, hyphens, ellipses, and exclamation marks. Regarding these, much of the information was already familiar. However, the section served as a reminder of some of the subtleties in usage. For example, the full stop is not used at the end of titles, and when ellipses are used (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 22). These seemingly small details are essential when writing academic essays. As such, the chapter was highly informative and a good refresher.

4) ENGLISH VARIANTS

In academic writing, paying particular attention to the variant one adheres to is essential. There are two main variants: Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). In addition to this broad categorization, the course pack goes into specific usage differences, including spelling, pronunciation, syntax, and punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25–29). Even though I have been using Standard American English in my writing, I was not aware of some slight differences between these variants. For instance, SBE uses inverted commas (") in place of quotation marks (""), and in SAE, periods and commas are placed inside closing quotation marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31–32). I have therefore found this chapter quite valuable in correcting my use of periods, commas, and quotation marks.

5) PLAGIARISM

The process of academic writing requires that we conduct a literature search and compile an original piece of work. For this reason, one will invariably use ideas from other authors in a specific field of research. Plagiarism is when one uses information and ideas from other authors without acknowledging them (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). The way to avoid plagiarism is by citing the source using quotations or paraphrasing and including a list of works cited (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 35–38). For me, this chapter highlighted a vital component of academic writing, that is, to keep our work original, which allows us to add value to the existing body of knowledge while at the same time giving credit to other authors in the field.

6) STYLE GUIDES

Style guides are a way to standardize the writing process so that there is coherence and consistency among different authors (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). Even though EUCLID recommends Chicago/Turabian style, other styles, such as WHO (World Health

Organization), are acceptable. Chapter 6 of the reading material goes into specific details on the Chicago Style. I found the sections on capitalization (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 45–46), compound words (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 46–47), and quotations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 48–50) to be quite instructive. In the past, I have only ever used the Harvard style, and I, therefore, feel that it will take me some time to get acquainted with the nuances of this style. I also appreciate that EUCLID does not restrict students to a particular style. This allows me to learn and use the WHO style especially given that my doctorate program is in a health-related field.

7) CONCLUSION

ACA-401D has given me an idea of what to expect in my doctoral degree journey regarding writing. My writing will have to be highly structured and systematic. To achieve this, I must learn and be comfortable with specific style guides as recommended by EUCLID. The learning material for ACA-401D lays the foundation and gives an overview of all the essential elements of academic writing. The material is an ideal primer for upcoming periods.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck and Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.